

Whitepaper:

2026 Revision –
Microfluidic devices:
Interoperability requirements for
dimensions, connections and initial device
classification

Work package 2

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1 Foreword

This document details proposed revisions to ISO 22916:2022. These revisions are intended to clarify interoperability requirements without restricting existing manufacturing approaches.

The main changes are as follows:

- More granular dimensions for device footprints
- Extended footprints for inclusion of clamping hardware
- A structured framework for communicating device footprint and port positions by text
- A structured framework for specifying requirements and properties of sub-regions of devices
- Adjustments to the text of the scope to clearly state that this document pertains to microfluidic interconnection and not connections to/between conventional fluid handling systems.
- The previously included device classifications will be expanded into a framework for specifying device operating window.
- Ambiguity will be removed from the text in several places

2 Introduction

This document was developed in response to the demand from the microfluidics community for minimum specifications for the interoperability of microfluidics devices and the complementary demand for clear standards on communication of device-specific interfacing requirements. These demands are driven by the fact that most microfluidics products are produced internally with custom dimensions and characteristics.

Microfluidics based diagnostics have been shown over the years to be viable alternatives to conventional macroscale analysis systems, and in some applications provide analytical capabilities which are not possible using macroscale systems. Furthermore, microfluidic devices are finding rapid uptake by end users in the fields of Organ-on-Chip and Microphysiological Systems. Hence, exploitation of microfluidics will play an important role for next generation of diagnostic and cell culture devices. However, there are many other (potential) applications for microfluidics, and also many technologies and materials being used. This diversity is a problem when it comes to combining microfluidic devices. Researchers, developers and system integrators do not want to spend much time on side issues like correct connection of devices; they also want to use devices from different suppliers without needing to change their whole experimental setup; and they want their developed products to go as smoothly as possible into production. Providers of analytical services do not want their limited laboratory space cluttered with a multitude of incompatible instruments. Chemical engineers want easy interconnection between pumps, sensors and reactors, and finally, operational managers want a second source for their products. In short interoperability and therefore standardizing the interfaces between them is important.

Another essential requirement for interoperability is the clear communication of device operating windows. From studies of the products on the market, temperature, pressure and flowrate have been identified as key operating parameters. Operating devices outside of the expected range of these parameters can result in device malfunction, therefore clear communication of the operating window to device integrators and users is critical. Standardized testing methods of these parameters is similarly expected to become increasingly important to ensure comparability of device operating windows. As such, typical ranges for these parameters have also been identified. These ranges will provide the boundary conditions for future tests to be developed. Ultimately, clear specification of the operating windows and uptake of standardized testing will lead to quicker acceptance of new devices by the market.

3 Scope

This document specifies requirements on microfluidic devices to facilitate their interfacing both with other microfluidic devices and with systems which require microfluidic interfacing. These requirements include dimensional constraints and frameworks for clearly communicating interfacing requirements to device integrators. Microfluidic devices which follow this standard can thereby be considered microfluidic building blocks (MFBBs).

This document pertains specifically to microfluidic devices which fit within a rectangular footprint and have a flat surface for fluidic interfacing on at least one face.

This document is applicable to devices in the field of “microfluidics” needing microfluidic interconnections. Connections to and between conventional (non-microfluidic) fluid handling systems are not the focus of this document.

4 General Dimensions and Tolerances

Table 1 and Table 2 present the recommended general dimensions and tolerances regarding port pitches, device thicknesses and port dimensions respectively for microfluidic devices with connections on primary and secondary face and for microfluidic devices with connections on side faces. In the tables and in the document n is an integer ≥ 1 .

Table 1: Key parameters for connections on primary and secondary faces

Dimensions in millimetres

Parameters	Nominal value	Minimal value	Maximal value	Tolerance
Reference point	(0; 0)			
Minimal distance of any port from any side of the device		3.00		± 0.15
Port pitch	$n \times 1.50$			$\pm 0.10^*$
Distance between rows of ports	$n \times 1.50$			$\pm 0.10^*$
Port diameter for 1,5 mm grid		0.4	0.7	
Port diameter for 3 mm grid		0.4	2.0	
Port diameter for 4,5 mm grid		0.4	3.5	
Tight tolerance of outer device dimension (desired)				± 0.05
Lower tolerance of outer device dimension				± 0.15
Minimum distance between port edge and outer edge of face	2.7			± 0.10

*NOTE: This tolerance applies to the port position with respect to the reference point, not to the pitch itself.

Table 2 : Key parameters for connections on side faces

Dimensions in millimetres

Parameters	Nominal value	Tolerance
Reference point	(0; 0; 0)	
Distance of the first port from the Z axis	3.00	±0.15
Port pitch	$n \times 1.50$	±0.10*
Total device thickness	0.80	±0.10
	1.00	±0.10
	1.10	±0.10
	1.40	±0.10
	1.80	±0.15
	2.00	±0.20
	4.00	±0.40
Tight tolerance of outer device dimension (desired)	$n \times 1.50$	±0.05
Lower tolerance of outer device dimension		±0.15

*NOTE: This tolerance applies to the port position with respect to the reference point, not to the pitch itself.

The tolerances specified in this clause are selected to balance achievable manufacturing accuracy with typical alignment and sealing requirements of microfluidic interconnection hardware. They are not intended to imply manufacturing capability limits.

5 Microfluidic device topology, nomenclature, reference point, and axes

5.1 Microfluidic device topology

The microfluidic devices described in this document are those which fit within a rectangular footprint and have a flat surface for fluidic interfacing on at least one face. Figure 1 describes the names for each face of the device.

The primary and secondary faces are those whose dimensions are defined by the device footprint, while the side faces are those surfaces which connect the primary and secondary faces. By default, of the two faces with dimensions defined by the device footprint, the primary face is the one with the most ports.

Figure 1: Schematics showing device face labelling

5.2 Default reference point and axes

This section defines the default reference point and axis definitions for microfluidic devices. Device specific reference points and axis may be otherwise defined by the device manufacturer as long as they are clearly stated in reference material provided with the device.

The width and length of the microfluidic device footprint define an X- and Y-axis. By default, the X-axis should be defined as the axis parallel to the row containing the largest number of ports. The reference point is the intersection of the X-axis and the Y-axis. With the X-axis pointing from left to right, the default reference point is at the top left of the primary face. Example is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: X-axis, Y-axis and R for devices with connections on the primary and secondary faces

In the case of side ports, the Z-axis shall also be taken into account. The bottom face is positioned on the X-Y plane. Figure 3 presents the reference point R for side ports.

Figure 3: X-axis, Y-axis and R for devices with side connections

Key

- X** | X-axis
- Y** | Y-axis
- Z** | Z-axis
- R** | reference point for side connections

a) Isometric view

b) Upper side view

When a device has rounded corners, the intersection of the extensions of X-axis and Y-axis should be used as the reference point by default.

6 Microfluidic device dimensions

6.1 Device thickness

When made of glass, the microfluidic device should have a thickness compatible with existing standard wafer thicknesses since they are readily available, cheaper and do not require polishing. Moreover, standard wafers have an excellent surface quality, which has a positive influence in manufacturability and yield.

Manufacturing constraints on chip thickness of polymer devices are less strict and are thereby not considered in this document.

The thickness is of relevance for side connection. If side connectors are to be used, it is recommended that neither top layer nor bottom layer be thinner than 0.4 mm (see Clause 8).

Some common thicknesses for bottom layer, t_1 , and top layer, t_2 , are given in Table 3 along with corresponding common final device thicknesses.

Table 3: Common thicknesses for bottom layer, t_1 , and top layer, t_2

Dimensions in millimetres

Total thickness		Top layer thickness							
		t_2							
		0.2	0.4	0.5	0.7	0.9	1.0	1.1	2.0
Bottom layer thickness t_1	0.2				0.9			1.3	
	0.4		0.8		1.1				
	0.5			1.0					
	0.7	0.9	1.1		1.4			1.8	
	0.9					1.8			
	1.0						2.0		
	1.1	1.3			1.8			2.2	
	2.0								4.0

NOTE: Devices may be comprised of more than two layers.

6.2 Device outer dimensions

To be considered compliant with this standard, a microfluidic device shall have outer dimensions of a multiple of 1.5 mm, or use one of the other special footprints detailed later in this clause. Outer dimensions shall be measured on the interfacing faces.

Figure 4 gives an example of a 15 mm × 15 mm microfluidic device with ports on the primary face featuring a 3 mm port pitch.

Figure 4: 15 mm × 15 mm microfluidic device (3 mm pitch)

Other examples of microfluidic devices outer dimensions are: 7.5 mm × 9.0 mm; 15 mm × 30 mm; 30 mm × 15 mm; 7.5 mm × 45 mm; 45 mm × 7.5 mm.

6.2.1 Device outer dimensions for microplate compatibility

To be compatible with a microplate footprint as defined in [Error! Reference source not found.](#) ANSI SLAS 1-2004, a microfluidic device shall have the outer dimensions given in Table 4 and illustrated in Figure 5.

Table 4: device outer dimensions for microplate compatibility

Dimensions in millimetres

Length	Width
127.76 ± 0.25	85.48 ± 0.25

NOTE: A related footprint of 127.5 x 85.5 is realizable using the outer device dimension increments (1.5 mm) detailed in **Table 1**. While this footprint may be preferred to the one specified in **Table 4**, depending on tolerances, it may break compliance with [ANSI SLAS 1-2004](#).

Figure 5: Microplate footprint (example with a 96 wells multiplate)

6.2.2 Device outer dimensions for microscope slide compatibility

To be compatible with microscope slide dimensions defined in ISO 8037-1, the microfluidic device shall be a rectangle with the outer dimensions given in Table 6.

Table 6: Outer device dimensions for microscope slide compatibility

Dimensions in millimetres

Format	Length	Width
Simple	$26 \begin{smallmatrix} +0 \\ -1 \end{smallmatrix}$	$76 \begin{smallmatrix} +0 \\ -1 \end{smallmatrix}$
Double	$52 \begin{smallmatrix} +0 \\ -1 \end{smallmatrix}$	$76 \begin{smallmatrix} +0 \\ -1 \end{smallmatrix}$

A slide format of 25.5 mm × 75.0 mm is within the tolerances stated in table 6 and aligns with a port grid of 1.5 mm. This format is therefore recommended as shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Preferred device outer dimensions for microscope slide

Dimensions in millimetres

Format	Length	Width
Normal size	25.5 ± 0.5	$75 \begin{smallmatrix} +1 \\ -0 \end{smallmatrix}$
Double size	$51 \begin{smallmatrix} +1 \\ -0 \end{smallmatrix}$	$75 \begin{smallmatrix} +1 \\ -0 \end{smallmatrix}$

6.2.3 Device outer dimensions for credit card footprint

A microfluidic device with a size similar to a credit card shall have outer dimensions of 84 mm × 54 mm. Figure 6 presents an examples of microfluidic device with a credit card footprint.

Figure 6: Microfluidic device on the credit card format

6.2.4 Extended Footprint for Built-in Clamping

A microfluidic device may also include features outside the footprint for clamping the device to a manifold. These features must be fully contained within a 6 mm margin surrounding the device footprint.

An example of a device using this extended footprint to include holes for clamping screws is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Device using the Extended Footprint for Built-in Clamping

7 Microfluidic ports on primary and secondary faces

7.1 General

Microfluidic connections on primary and secondary faces address design requirements for microfluidic devices that are intended to be inter connected to primary and/or secondary face of the device, depending on the interfacing method used.

The manufacturer shall choose the port pitch, the port diameter, the distance between ports and edges, and the port nomenclature as specified in this document to ensure compatibility with interconnected microfluidic devices.

7.2 Port pitch

In case of multiple fluidic ports, the pitch between two ports shall be a multiple of 1.5 mm indifferent of the X-axis or in Y-axis. This configuration defines a grid of rows and columns of potential port positions. The rows are parallel to the X-axis and the columns are parallel to the Y-axis. While the port pitch may be any multiple of 1.5 mm, a 3 mm pitch should be considered as the default value for typical microfluidic devices. The selected pitch shall be maintained consistently across the face.

7.3 Port diameter

The port diameter shall follow the relation between port pitch and port diameter according to Table 8.

Table 8: Relation between ports pitch and port diameter

Dimensions in millimetres

Port pitch	Minimum port diameter	Maximum port diameter
1.5	0.4	0.7
3	0.4	2.0
4.5	0.4	3.5

In order to ensure other properties (e.g. leak free, blocking, loaded volume) additional requirements may be specified by the device manufacturer.

7.4 Distance between ports and edges

The edge of any port shall be at least 2.7 mm away from the edge of the device to allow space for interfacing.

7.5 Port nomenclature

The row name shall be a letter in alphabetical order from the reference point.

The columns name shall be a number starting at 1 from the reference point.

Figure 8 presents an example of nomenclature with a grid of 1.5 mm: ports A1, A2, C1 and C3 on a 1.5 mm grid.

In the case where there are more than 26 rows, double letters can be used to denote the port row, e.g. the 28th row is denoted AB and the 29th row is denoted AC.

Figure 8: Port nomenclature of a microfluidic device

Dimensions in millimetres

7.6 Interfacing exclusion zone

In order to achieve leak free microfluidic connection, other structures that create obstructions on the surface of the device should not be included within 3 mm of the nearest port. This defines an exclusion zone around the ports. Structures that create obstructions to interfacing on the surface include, but are not limited to any structures that create holes, dents or protrusions on the surface (with the only exception being other fluidic ports). Figure 9 presents examples of exclusion zones around ports for a device of 15 mm × 15 mm.

Figure 9: Exclusion zones around ports for a 15 mm × 15 mm device

7.7 Clamping exclusion zone

If a microfluidic device is designed to be held in place by an external clamp (rather than to built-in clamping as described in Section 6.2.4), a 1 mm wide strip at the opposite face of the device (e.g. primary face in case of connections on the secondary face) shall be reserved for clamping purposes. This area shall be free of obstructing structures. Figure 10 presents the clamping exclusion zone for a 15 mm × 15 mm microfluidic device.

Figure 10: Clamping exclusion zone for a microfluidic device of 15 mm × 15 mm (primary/secondary face connections)

Dimensions in millimetres

NOTE Although a clamping exclusion zone of 1 mm wide is sufficient for devices with sizes of 15 mm × 15 mm or smaller, for larger devices a wider clamping zone may be needed. Some applications can also require larger clamping zones depending on the expected operational pressure.

8 Microfluidic side ports

8.1 General

This section addresses design requirements on microfluidic devices for including microfluidic connections on the side faces of a device.

8.2 Port pitch

The port pitch for the side connections is similar to that for the primary/secondary face connections (see 0).

The recommended port pitch is 3 mm.

A 1.5 mm pitch may also be used, but can impose additional constraints on device integrators, requiring multiport connectors and/or direct coupling (e.g. gluing) of tubing to the interface.

8.3 Port size and shape

The port size and port shape are not defined, as the process to make the channels on the microfluidic device defines them.

The position of the centre point in Z-direction depends on the process, the design and the thickness of the two layers.

The entire port shall be located within a circle centred on the defined pitch with a diameter of 0.5 mm. The positional tolerance defined herein refers to the interface geometry and does not imply constraints on internal channel geometry.

8.4 Distance between ports and edges

In case of a minimum pitch of 1.5 mm, the centre of a fluidic port shall be at a minimum distance of 3 mm from the edges in the Z-direction.

8.5 Port nomenclature

For side connections, there is usually only one row of ports, row A.

The columns name shall be a number starting at 1 from the reference point.

8.6 Clamping exclusion zone

To ensure a leak tight and mechanically strong connection, exclusion zones shall be included along the edges bounding faces containing side connections. In particular a zone of 3 mm from the edge of the chip shall be reserved for the support and clamping of the device. In these zones, optical structures or protruding structures are not allowed. Figure 11 presents the clamping zone for a 15 mm × 30 mm microfluidic device with side connections on two side faces.

Figure 11: Clamping zone for a microfluidic device of 15 mm × 30 mm (side connections)

9 Designated areas and points

9.1 Designated areas

Areas may be designated in which specified features are present or specified requirements must be met. For such a designated area, the specification for the area shall be provided with the device and should be used by device integrators.

Example area specifications include:

- "Optical access is required in this area for sensor readout"
- "One watt of heat will be dissipated over this area during device operation"
- "This area is left open to receive a removable membrane used for cell culture"

A designated area must be given a unique name and its location must be clearly communicated with respect to the reference point. The dimensions of the area and whether it is on the primary or secondary face of the device shall also be clearly specified. An example diagram used to communicate this information is shown in Figure 12. The same spatial information may be encoded in a text string, for example: "AreaName_Ax,Ay,Primary,w,h".

Figure 12: Device with a Designated Area

9.2 Designated points

A microfluidic device may have points designated in which specified features are present or specified restrictions must be met. The specification for the point shall be provided with the device and should be used by device integrators.

Some example specifications follow:

- "1 mm diameter pad for electrical connection"
- "1 mm diameter receptacle for optical fiber integration"
- "Hole for M2 bolt to clamp the device to a fluidic manifold"

A designated point must be given a unique name and its location must be clearly communicated with respect to the reference point. An example diagram used to communicate this information is shown in Figure 13. The same spatial information may be encoded in a text string, for example: "PointName_Px,Py,Primary".

Figure 13: Device with a Designated Point

10 Communication of Layout Information

To facilitate integration of microfluidic devices, certain information regarding the device layout may be communicated in the format described in this section.

The format contains:

- The footprint (in accordance with dimensions defined in clause 6)
- Indication of whether the device has built-in clamping
- The grid layout that is used for the port locations (in accordance with dimensions defined in clause 7.2)
- Which ports on that grid are present (in accordance with nomenclature defined in clause 7.5)
- Port diameter and an indication of which face the ports are located on

The format shown in Figure 14 should be used to communicate this information in a single human readable string which can be referred to as a device's Chip Layout and Interfacing Ports String (CLIP-String).

Figure 14: Symbolic representation of a CLIP-String

Definitions of the symbols used in figure 14 follows here:

Footprint:

- F_x - footprint in x-direction (in mm)
- F_y - footprint in y-direction (in mm)
- c - presence indicates built-in clamping (optional)

Grid:

- G_x - grid origin x (in mm)
- G_y - grid origin y (in mm)
- G_p - grid pitch (in mm)

Sets of Ports:

- f - indicates if the set is on the primary face ('p') or on the secondary face ('s')
- D - port diameter for the set (in μm)
- R - the port location letter (row)
- C - the port location number (column)

Letters and numbers are used to indicate port rows and columns as defined in clause 7.5.

Ranges of port locations can be indicated using a dash. Ports and port ranges are separated by commas. Sets of ports on the same face with the same diameter are separated by underscores. Decimal points are included before the tenths place when needed. The CLIP string may contain as many sets of ports as needed.

A worked out example of a CLIP String for a fictitious device layout is shown in figure 15 below.

Figure 15: Example CLIP string and annotated layout of described layout

Note: annotations on the layout in figure 15 are included to assist understating of the CLIP String but are not required by this standard unless specified as a requirement in other clauses. See Annex A for practical examples of CLIP Strings and resulting layouts.

11 Operating Window

A microfluidic device manufacturer may communicate the expected operating window for their device using the following framework. Parameters included in this definition of an operating window are: the pressure of the fluid(s), temperature, and flow rate. The framework is detailed in Table 9.

Note that some devices use capillary forces to generate flow internally. In this case the operating window for flow rate may be specified as "capillary".

Table 9: Example of application classes

Operating Window	Maximum pressure Pa	Minimum temperature °C	Maximum temperature °C	Maximum flowrate μL/min
PTF 2/4-50/10	2×10^5	4	50	10
PTF 2/4-75/100	2×10^5	4	75	100
PTF 2/4-100/100	2×10^5	4	100	100
PTF 2/4-75/C	2×10^5	4	75	capillary-driven
^a NOTE 1 bar = 10^5 Pa = 100 000 Pa.				

Manufacturers may include appropriate certification or test results to indicate that their devices operate successfully within the claimed operating window.

In the case of flow rate testing, different tests may be considered for the different flow regimes. Suggested tests for typical flow regimes are:

1. Low flow rate: 1 nl/min to 1 μl/min -> calibration by optical methods preferably, or low-flow volumetric methods with 2 % uncertainty.
2. Middle flow rate: 1 μl/min to 100 μl/min (hot spot) -> calibration by gravimetric or volumetric methods with 0.5 % uncertainty.
3. High flow rate: 100 μl/min to 10 ml/min -> calibration by gravimetric methods with 0.1 % uncertainty.

Annex A: Example footprints

CLIP String:

75.5x25.5_4,6,4.5_p500,A-D2,A-D15

Annotated Layout:

CLIP String:

75.5x25.5_4,6,4.5_p500,A-D1-2,A-D15-16

Annotated Layout:

CLIP String:

75.5x25.5_4,3.75,4.5_p500,A1-16,E1-16

Annotated Layout:

CLIP String:

15x15_3,3,4.5_p500,A1-3,C1-3

Annotated Layout:

CLIP String:

15x15_3,3,4.5_p500,A1,A3,C1,C3

Annotated Layout:

CLIP String:

15x15_3,3,4.5_p500,A1,C3

Annotated Layout:

CLIP String:

30x30_6,4.5,3_p500,A1,A3,A5,A7,H1,H3,H5,H7

Annotated Layout:

CLIP String:

30x30c_6,4.5,3_p500,A1,A3,A5,A7,H1,H3,H5,H7

Annotated Layout:

CLIP String:

30x15_4.5,4.5,1.5_p500,A1,A15,E1,E15

Annotated Layout:

CLIP String:

30x15c_4.5,4.5,1.5_p500,A1,A8,A15,E1,E8,E15

Annotated Layout:

CLIP String:

15x15_4.5,4.5,6_p500,A-B1-2

Annotated Layout:

CLIP String:

15x15c_4.5,4.5,6_p500,A-B1-2

Annotated Layout:

